

Revisiting the np_x Control Chart: Performance Insights and the Impact of Parameter Estimation

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Abstract

The np_x control chart, introduced by Wu et al. (2009), was designed to monitor the mean of a continuous variable using attribute inspection. While this approach offers advantages such as simplicity and cost-effectiveness, our re-examination reveals inconsistencies in prior performance assessments and provides new insights. Specifically, we demonstrate that for a two-sided np_x chart to outperform the traditional \bar{X} chart, the required sample size must be significantly larger than what was recommended. Additionally, in practice, control charts are typically designed using estimated parameters, yet prior studies on the np_x chart assume known parameters. We extend the analysis to this more realistic setting, showing that parameter estimation inflates the in-control average time to a signal (ATS_0), leading to a higher-than-expected false alarm rate. Through theoretical derivations and numerical studies, we identify conditions where the np_x chart remains competitive and propose strategies to mitigate estimation effects. These findings refine our understanding of attribute-based control charts for mean monitoring and offer practical guidance for their implementation.

Key Words: Parameter Estimation, False Alarm Rate, Average Time to a Signal, Attribute control charts, np_x chart Control Chart

1. Introduction

It is widely recognized that product quality is a key factor in determining the success of a business in a competitive environment. Therefore, it is crucial for companies to monitor and control certain quality characteristics of their products. Statistical Process Control (SPC) provides a range of tools for this purpose (Montgomery, 2012). Among these, control charts are widely used to track changes in process quality characteristics, such as the process mean (Aykroyd et al., 2019).

When the quality characteristic of interest is qualitative or cannot be easily measured numerically, attribute control charts — such as p, np, and c charts — are commonly employed. In these charts, product quality is assessed by attributes, typically classifying items as conforming or non-conforming. This classification may be performed through visual inspection or by using a go/no-go gauge, for instance (Castagliola & Wu, 2012; Tiplica, 2015).

Despite the wide application of attribute control charts, traditional methods can have limitations when dealing with processes where the probability of nonconformity varies over time or when sample sizes are small. Recent research has explored modifications and alternative designs to improve the sensitivity and efficiency of these charts, allowing for more accurate detection of shifts in process quality (e.g., Aykroyd et al., 2019).

Wu et al. (2009) introduced the np_x Control Chart, which uses a go/no-go gauge to monitor the process mean of a continuous variable. Unlike the traditional \bar{X} Control Chart, which requires precise measurement of the quality characteristic, the np_x Chart classifies units as conforming or nonconforming, offering a simpler and more cost-effective alternative. Wu et al. (2009) demonstrated that this chart can outperform the \bar{X} Chart simply by doubling the sample size, and their work has been widely cited, reflecting its practical relevance.

In this approach, the quality characteristic X is assumed to follow a normal distribution, $X \sim N(\mu, \sigma_0)$. Each unit is inspected using a go/no-go gauge, and two key design parameters define the chart. The upper control limit (UCL) specifies the maximum number of nonconforming units allowed in a sample of size n . The warning limits, w_L and w_U , are determined by a constant k_W according to:

$$w_L = \mu_0 - k_W \sigma_0 \text{ and } w_U = \mu_0 + k_W \sigma_0 \quad (1)$$

These parameters are selected to achieve two performance goals: an in-control Average Time to Signal (ATS_0) of 370 and the minimum Extra Quadratic Loss (EQL), which measures out-of-control performance across a range of shifts.

Despite its advantages, prior studies on the np_x Chart assumed known parameters and recommended sample sizes that may underestimate the requirements for two-sided charts. In practice, control charts are typically designed using estimated parameters, which can inflate the in-control average time to signal (ATS_0) and increase the false alarm rate. This study revisits the np_x Chart, examining its performance under parameter estimation and providing new insights into its practical implementation. Through theoretical derivations and numerical studies, we identify conditions under which the np_x Chart remains competitive and propose strategies to mitigate the effects of parameter estimation.

This proceedings note is part of a broader research project. A full-length manuscript — containing complete derivations, estimation-case results, sensitivity analyses, and extended tables/figures — is being prepared for submission to a peer-reviewed journal. Here we report only the essential findings that support our JSM 2025 presentation.

2. The np_x Control Chart - Known parameters Case

Wu et al. (2009) proposed the np_x chart, which employs an attribute inspection to monitor the mean value of a quality characteristic variable X arguing that the np_x chart may be quicker and cheaper than the \bar{X} chart. To make this comparison more appropriate and fairer, Wu et al. (2009) suggested that both charts are equivalent when have similar performance detection (such as the ATS) and the following equation is true.

$$\frac{c_{\bar{X}} n_{\bar{X}}}{h_{\bar{X}}} = \frac{c_{np} n_{np}}{h_{np}} \quad (2)$$

Where $c_{\bar{x}}$ and c_{np} are the inspection cost per unit, $n_{\bar{x}}$ and n_{np} are the sample size, $h_{\bar{x}}$ and h_{np} are the sampling interval, respectively for the \bar{X} chart and np_x chart. As Wu et al. (2009) pointed out “the inspection cost c_{np} required by an np_x chart is lower than the inspection cost $c_{\bar{x}}$ required by an \bar{X} chart in many SPC applications. According to Eq. (2), the sample size n_{np} of the np_x chart may be allowed to be larger than $n_{\bar{x}}$ of the \bar{X} chart, and/or the sampling interval h_{np} be smaller than $h_{\bar{x}}$ ”.

Wu et al. (2009) designed the two-sided np_x chart, displayed on section 2 of their paper. Where the number of nonconforming (D) units on the chart are compared to the upper control limit of np_x chart (UCL_{np_x}). The UCL_{np_x} is the maximum number of nonconforming units (D) accepted in a sample. Thus, if D is greater than UCL_{np_x} the process is signaled as out of control.

The fraction of nonconforming items in a sample (p), classified by the go/no go gauge, follows a normal distribution, leading to equation 3.

$$p = \Pr(D < w_L \text{ or } D > w_U) = 1 - \phi(k_w - \delta) + \phi(-k_w - \delta) \quad (3)$$

where $\phi()$ is the cumulative probability function of the standard normal distribution.

The number of nonconforming units follow a binomial distribution, so the probability that the number D of nonconforming units in a sample is larger than UCL_{np_x} for a given fraction nonconforming p, is demonstrated on equation 3:

$$P(p) = \Pr(D > UCL_{np_x} | p) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{UCL_{np_x}} C_i^{n_{np}} p^i (1-p)^{n_{np}-i} \quad (4)$$

The performance can be measured about the average time to a signal when the process is in-control (ATS_0), equation 5.

$$ATS_0 = \frac{h}{\alpha} = \frac{h}{P(p_0)} \quad (5)$$

When the process is out-of-control, the performance is given by $ATS(\delta)$, equation 6.

$$ATS(\delta) = (ARL - 0.5)h_{np} \quad (6)$$

Instead of using the $ATS(\delta)$ as an objective function, the authors use the extra quadratic loss (EQL) as the overall out-of-control measure and assumed that a shift range are equally important, equation 7.

$$EQL = \frac{1}{\delta_{max} - \delta_{min}} \int_{\delta_{min}}^{\delta_{max}} \delta^2 ATS(\delta) d\delta \quad (7)$$

The optimal parameters UCL_{np_x} and k_w are obtained so that the ATS_0 is equal to 370 and the EQL is minimized.

We reassess the known-parameter performance of the np_x chart under the same goals used by Wu et al. (2009): target in-control Average Time to Signal $ATS_0 = 370$ and out-of-control efficiency measured by the Extra Quadratic Loss (EQL). For a fair comparison to

the \bar{X} chart, we use identical inspection cost per unit time, allowing either larger n or shorter sampling interval h for the np_x chart while holding performance targets fixed.

Recomputing ATS_0 and $ATS(\delta)$ for the two-sided np_x design under Wu et al.'s settings shows their published ATS_0 is overly optimistic; when corrected, the np_x chart signals more often than expected. Consequently, the statement that “doubling n ” suffices for the np_x chart to outperform the \bar{X} chart does not hold in the two-sided case. Table 1 summarizes the key comparison for the baseline \bar{X} design with $n_{\bar{X}} = 6$.

Table 1. Replication snapshot for the two-sided np_x chart under equal cost per time ($ATS_0 = 370$)

$n_{\bar{X}}$	n_{np_x}	k_W	Reported ATS_0 (Wu et al., 2009)	Our ATS_0
6	6	1.27	370	55.64
6	12	0.75	370	8.88
6	38	1.66	—	370

The first two rows reproduce Wu et al.'s n_{np_x} choices; once ATS_0 is correctly evaluated, these designs fall far short of $ATS_0 = 370$. The third row shows a feasible np_x design that does meet $ATS_0 = 370$. However, it requires much larger n_{np_x} (here, 38), so merely doubling n is insufficient in the two-sided case.

Given this, we propose compact rules for the minimum sample size of the np_x chart to match or exceed the \bar{X} chart:

$$n_{np_x}^{(2s)} \approx n_{\bar{X}}(n_{\bar{X}} + 1) \quad (8)$$

$$n_{np_x}^{(1s)} \approx [1.6 n_{\bar{X}}] \quad (9)$$

Equation (8) captures the quadratic growth needed for the two-sided np_x to be competitive (e.g., $n_{\bar{X}} = 6 \Rightarrow n_{np_x} \approx 42$, consistent with the order of magnitude in Table 1), whereas Eq. (9) shows that in the one-sided case the np_x chart can be competitive with a modest increase in n (e.g., $n_{\bar{X}} = 10 \Rightarrow n_{np_x} \approx 16$).

Under equal inspection cost per unit time and $ATS_0 = 370$, the two-sided np_x requires substantially larger samples (or shorter h) than suggested by Wu et al. (2009), whereas the one-sided np_x often becomes attractive with only a modest increase in n . For space reasons, we omit large tables and direct readers to the extended paper/slide deck for full numerical evidence.

3. The np_x Control Chart - Unknown parameters Case

To evaluate the performance of the np_x Control Chart under realistic conditions, we conduct numerical simulations incorporating parameter estimation, which is commonly

encountered in practice. Specifically, we examine how using sample estimates of the process mean and standard deviation influences the in-control Average Time to a Signal (ATS_0) and the false alarm rate.

Control charts are typically designed in a Phase I study, using m samples of size n to ensure that data are collected from an in-control process (Chakraborti & Human, 2008).

In this study, to estimate the mean, we used the overall sample mean estimator ($\bar{\bar{X}}$) and to estimate the standard deviation, we considered the pooled sample standard deviation estimator (S_p). Table 2 shows the details of this estimation process.

Table 2: Iterative process to estimate the mean and the variance of a process (Phase I)

Sample j	Observations					Sample Mean	Sample Variance
Sample 1	X_{11}	X_{12}	X_{13}	...	X_{1n}	\bar{X}_1	S_1^2
Sample 2	X_{21}	X_{22}	X_{23}	...	X_{2n}	\bar{X}_2	S_2^2
Sample 3	X_{31}	X_{32}	X_{33}	...	X_{3n}	\bar{X}_3	S_3^2
...
Sample m	X_{m1}	X_{m2}	X_{m3}	...	X_{mn}	\bar{X}_m	S_m^2
						$\bar{\bar{X}}$	\bar{S}^2

The process mean is estimated using the overall sample mean:

$$\hat{\mu}_0 = \bar{\bar{X}} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \bar{X}_i, \quad \bar{X}_i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n X_{ij} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (10)$$

$$\hat{\sigma}_0 = S_p = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m S_i^2} \quad \text{where} \quad S_i^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{j=1}^n (X_{i,j} - \bar{X}_i)^2 \quad (11)$$

The warning limits for the np_x chart are now computed as:

$$\hat{w}_L = \hat{\mu}_0 - k_W \hat{\sigma}_0 = \bar{\bar{X}} - k_W S_p, \quad \hat{w}_U = \hat{\mu}_0 + k_W \hat{\sigma}_0 = \bar{\bar{X}} + k_W S_p$$

where $S_{pooled} = S_p = \sqrt{\bar{S}^2}$.

Now, the probability of X be classified as nonconforming when process is in-control (\hat{p}_0) is also a random variable, equation 12.

$$\hat{p}_0 = 1 - P(\hat{w}_L \leq X \leq \hat{w}_U) = 1 - \phi\left(\frac{Z}{\sqrt{mn}} + k_W \sqrt{\frac{Y}{m(n-1)}}\right) + \phi\left(\frac{Z}{\sqrt{mn}} - k_W \sqrt{\frac{Y}{m(n-1)}}\right) \quad (12)$$

where Z follows a standard normal distribution and Y a chi-squared distribution with $m(n-1)$ degrees of freedom.

The performance of the np_x chart in terms of ATS_0 and FAR depend on \hat{p}_0 and are conditioned on the estimation of the parameters. Thus, they are denoted by $CATS_0$ and $CFAR$ (check Jardim et al., (2020)). See their definition on equation 13.

$$CATS_0 = \frac{h}{CFAR} = \frac{h}{1 - \sum_{i=0}^{UCL_{np_x}} \frac{np_x!}{(np_x - i)!} \hat{p}_0^i (1 - \hat{p}_0)^{np_x - i}} \quad (13)$$

Note that $CATS_0$ and $CFAR$ are random variables and they change from practitioner to practitioner.

To study the distribution of $CATS_0$, we simulated 100,000 values of $CATS_0$ considering different numbers of samples (m), each one of sample size 38, $h = 1$, $UCL_{np_x} = 9$ and $k_w = 1.6599319$, see Table 3.

Table 3: $CATS_0$ Statistics

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Median	0.25 Quantile	0.75 Quantile
$m = 25$	439.14	300.30	360.05	243.53	541.69
$m = 50$	402.34	180.31	365.43	276.13	486.14
$m = 100$	385.78	118.47	367.48	301.80	449.64
$m = 500$	372.75	49.58	369.18	337.91	403.97
$m = 1000$	371.05	34.85	369.32	346.55	393.34

It can be observed that for 25 samples the mean of $CATS_0$ (439.14) is far from the desirable number of 370.4 and the standard deviation is large (300.30). If the number of samples is increased to 500, the $CATS_0$ is much closer to 372.75 and the standard deviation is much smaller, 49.58.

Figure 1 – Simulation of 100,000 $CATS_0$ for different numbers of samples m used to estimate the mean and the variance.

Thus, as many samples we can use to estimate the $CATS_0$, the result will be closer to the desirable, see Figure 1. So, one can clearly see that when m is small, the performance of the np_x chart is severely affected in terms of the $CATS_0$.

In practice, it is very difficult to have so many samples to estimate the parameters of the process. It is usually used 25 samples, making the dispersion of the $CATS_0$ large (check Table 3). To solve this problem, we used an optimization approach to find k_w and UCL_{np_x} for some values of n and m so that the expected value of $CARL_0$ is fixed on 370.4 and the expected value of EQL must be the minimum.

Table 4 shows the adjusted parameters k_W and UCL_{np_x} varying the sample size ($n = 5, 10, 15, 20$ and 25) and the number of samples used in Phase I (m).

Table 4 - k_W and UCL_{np_x} which satisfy the constraint $ATS_0 = \tau = 370$ for the np_x chart when the mean is estimated and the standard deviation is known for different number of samples m .

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
				$h = 1$		
		$m = 25$	$m = 50$	$m = 100$	$m = 500$	$m = 1000$
n=5	UCL	2	2	2	2	2
	k_w	1.78051	1.80627	1.81936	1.82999	1.83132
	EQL	9.213	9.461	9.584	9.683	9.695
n=10	UCL	3	3	3	3	3
	k_w	1.81566	1.83101	1.83877	1.84502	1.84580
	EQL	6.332	6.431	6.481	6.521	6.526
n=15	UCL	4	4	4	4	4
	k_w	1.79209	1.80354	1.80931	1.81395	1.81453
	EQL	5.223	5.284	5.315	5.339	5.342
n=20	UCL	5	5	5	5	5
	k_w	1.76338	1.77272	1.77742	1.78119	1.78166
	EQL	4.610	4.654	4.676	4.694	4.696
n=25	UCL	7	7	7	7	7
	k_w	1.61665	1.62401	1.62770	1.63066	1.63103
	EQL	4.215	4.249	4.266	4.280	4.281

4. Conclusions

This paper re-examined the np_x chart under a fair cost-per-time comparison with the \bar{X} chart and revisited earlier findings. When the chart is two-sided, our replication shows that the sample sizes previously suggested in the literature are not sufficient; substantially larger samples are needed for performance to match or surpass the traditional alternative. By contrast, in the one-sided setting the np_x chart can be competitive with only a modest increase in sample size.

We also studied the more realistic case in which the process mean and variability are estimated from preliminary data. In this setting, the in-control behavior varies across practitioners and can deviate from the nominal target when the preliminary sample is small. Increasing the amount of preliminary data reduces this variability, and simple adjustments to the chart's limits can recover the intended behavior while keeping good detection capability.

This proceedings note focuses on essential insights that support our JSM 2025 presentation. A longer manuscript, now in preparation, provides full derivations, extended simulations, and additional tables and figures.

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